

Roles of continental mid-lithosphere discontinuity in the craton instability under variable tectonic regimes

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1. Datasets of the numerical models as shown in manuscript and supporting information

Model-1-Reference-wet-olivine.zip

Model-2-Reference-antigorite.zip

Model-3-Extension-wet-olivine.zip

Model-4-Extension-wet-olivine-50Myr.zip

Model-5-Extension-antigorite.zip

Model-6-Extension-depleted-wet-olivine.zip

Model-7-Extension-depleted-antigorite.zip

Model-8-Compression-wet-olivine.zip

Model-9-Compression-antigorite.zip

Model-10-MantleFlow-wet-olivine.zip

Model-11-MantleFlow-antigorite.zip

Model-12-MantlePlume-wet-olivine-T400D200.zip

Model-13-MantlePlume-antigorite-T400D200.zip

Model-14-MantlePlume-antigorite-T400D100.zip

Model-15-MantlePlume-depleted-antigoriteT400D200.zip

Model-16-MantlePlume-depleted-antigoriteT400D300.zip

Model-17-MantlePlume-antigorite-T400D200-100Myr.zip

Models-Variable-MantlePlume-fertile-wet-olivine.zip

Models-Variable-MantlePlume-fertile-antigorite.zip

Models-Variable-MantlePlume-layered-antigorite.zip

Models-Variable-MantlePlume-depleted-antigorite.zip

2. Dataset of the nature of the MLD in Figure 1

Dataset-MLD.zip

**3. Database of the water capacity of mantle rock and shear-wave velocity (V_s) in
Figure S1, Figure S2**

Database-WaterCapacity.zip

Database- V_s .zip